

CHAPTER 3: SOUTH SUDAN'S LEGAL PLURALISM; CUSTOMARY LAW AND COURTS

3.1 Introduction

South Sudanese legal system is identified as a pluralistic legal system in which African customary law applies alongside statutory law. The applicability of these two laws is based on the phrase that customary law should be applied in courts if it is not contrary to justice, equity and good conscience. Customary law is widely accepted in South Sudan and is referred to as the body of customs and traditions utilized by and unites the majority of citizens in their jurisdiction. Customary law, therefore, is a set of rules, regulations, norms and usages existing among South Sudanese communities since time immemorial. It is obligatory and is widely applied in the country.

The South Sudanese dual justice system; formal courts and customary law courts apply concurrently in a parallel manner in both rural and urban centers¹. Bifurcated justice systems have colonial origins for colonial rule and establishment of social order among the colonized. Throughout history of South Sudan, there has been a limited prescribed interaction between the two justice systems. However, the current constitutional dispensation gives a huge room for interaction and both systems are recognized constitutionally.

The customary justice system has been the primary source of social order and stability within the country, even though the formal courts and statutory laws have been in use in South Sudan from the Anglo-Egyptian colonization era. The customary justice system has, therefore,

¹ Valfredo, Ruben SP. "Domesticating Treaties in the Legal System of South Sudan—A Monist or Dualist Approach?." *African Journal of International and Comparative Law* 28, no. 3 (2020):

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been cementing the togetherness of communities and tries and form a bridge between the many and varied tribal groups making up the population of the country. Customary laws vary from one community to the other but with similarity in customary laws, and as such, customary law courts function in similar ways. This forms the main reason why most dispute resolutions are overwhelmingly handled within local communities by tribal authorities under the customary justice system.

Before 1980, the judiciary of South Sudan was made up of two separate divisions; the Civil Division headed by the chief justice and the Sharia Division headed by the Chief qadi. The civil courts handled all criminal and most civil cases. On the other hand, the sharia courts, consisted of religious judges trained in Islamic law, handled Muslim matters of personal status including inheritance, marriage, divorce and family relations. The 1980 executive order consolidated the civil and Sharia courts to create a single High Court of Appeal replacing the Supreme Court and the Office of the Chief Qadi. Under the initial dispensation, judges applied civil and sharia law as a single code of law. Since 1983, the High Court of appeal and lower courts were required to exclusively apply Islamic law. The 1985 overthrow of Nimeiri was followed by suspension of application of the harsher *hudud* punishments in criminal cases. Each district or province had its own appeal, major and magistrate's courts. Serious crimes were handled by major courts convened by specific order of the provincial judge and was made up of a three magistrates' bench. Magistrates were categorized as first, second or third class and had corresponding criminal jurisdiction gradation. The magistrates were advised by the Police on prosecution preparation, whether a case goes to trail and also acted as legal advisers to defendants.

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The customary law courts handled over 90% of cases in South Sudan even when the Sharia courts were in place. Nationally, dispute resolution through the customary justice are at 60% due to their accessibility and flexibility in their procedures and sanctions adopting a restorative approach and emphasis on reconciliation, compensation, restoration and rehabilitation. The restorative approach employed by customary law courts is in line with Section 98 (3) (c) and (d) of the Local Government Act of 2009. In Accordance with the section, the Customary law courts inter alia apply the principles of adequate compensation to the victims of wrongs, voluntary mediation and reconciliation, agreements between parties are recognized and enforced in deciding cases.

The formal justice system remains challenging to access since it is expensive and difficult to understand coupled with delays at all stages due to sheer number of cases and few courts and judges. These reasons are why the customary law system is preferred over the formal one. Despite the distinct hierarchy of judicial systems, the courts work complementarily together though inconsistent and confusing. The statutory law courts form the top tiers of the hierarchy and provide appeal avenue from customary law courts.

3.2 Judicial System in South Sudan

The country has a dual judicial system consisting of statutory and customary law system. The two systems concurrently operate in a parallel manner at urban and rural areas respectively. The customary law courts make their rulings according to the customary laws of the respective ethnic groups while the formal courts are guided by the principles laid down by the statutes in

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the dispute resolution roles. There is no clear relationship between the two court systems². The customary law courts are more inclined and linked to the executive branch than the judiciary despite being subordinate and answerable to statutory courts. This is because the customary law courts are established and regulated by the Local Government Act and are administered by the Local Government at the County level. This development has been seen as undermining the capacity of formal courts to monitor and supervise the judicial function of customary law courts.

The Judiciary of South Sudan faces a number of challenges in its role to deliver justice. South Sudan adopted English as the official language and common law as its legal system upon coming into a constitutional force³. It should be noted that majority of the judges and lawyers in South Sudan were trained in Arabic language under the old Sudan's Sharia based civil law system and as a result lack language skill to practice in English. This developed has since undermined the ability of the judiciary to deliver justice and resulted in uneven legal practice in the country.

3.3 Court Structure

The supreme court is the apex court and the custodian of the constitutions and state constitutions. It is consisted by the Chief Justice, the Deputy Chief Justice and other five justices. The decisions of the supreme court are final and binding in all courts including the customary

² Babiker, Mohamed A. "Customary Law and Courts in the Context of Sudan's Legal Pluralism: Marginalized or Empowered under English Common Law and Islamic Law?." In *Anthropology of Law in Muslim Sudan*

³ Ndoromo, Owen, and Jean d'Amour Banyanga. "Cultural impact and an intimate partner aggression in African societies: A comparison of Rwanda and South Sudan." *European Journal of Social Sciences* 1, no. 3 (2018)

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law courts⁴. The supreme court is vested with exclusive and original jurisdiction to adjudicate on any legal disputes arising either under national and state constitutions. The Court also undertakes reviews and cassations on any criminal, civil or administrative matter arising within and without the law, law interpretations and judicial review power. The supreme court sits in three judge panels on each matter except for constitutional issues which require a quorum of at least nine judges. The decisions are based a simple majority and are final and binding.

The court of appeal is second to the Supreme Court and is made up of the president and other four justices. The court has three branches located in Juba, Malakal and Rumbek and take appeals from the high courts and their decisions are not final as they can be appealed against at the Supreme Court.

Each of the ten states of South Sudan has a high court. The recent expansion of states from ten to thirty-two resulted in twenty-two states without high courts. The High Courts are vested with exclusive and original jurisdiction over all murder cases and entertain appeals from the Country Courts⁵.

The county courts are lower, just below the high courts, and are present in each county. With the recent expansion of states, many county courts have been established with the creation of the new counties. The County Courts have original jurisdictions limited to criminal cases carrying sentences of seven or fewer year imprisonment and fine not exceeding 5000 SSP, in

⁴ Idris, Iffat. "Local governance in South Sudan: overview.

⁵ Pendle, Naomi. "Learning from Customary Law." *The Struggle for South Sudan: Challenges of Security and State Formation* (2018)

accordance with the code of criminal procedure. There is a constitutional room for creation of more courts and tribunals as deemed necessary⁶.

The customary courts systems are recognized by the constitution as institutions and their role in traditional authority⁷. The courts were formally established under the Local Government Act of 2009. The customary courts are presided over by traditional chiefs and the cases are decided in accordance with customs, norms, traditions and ethics of the respective communities⁸. The courts are quick in decision making and are easily accessible in comparison with statutory courts as over ninety per cent of disputes are resolved by these courts⁹. The Local Government Act of 2009 Section 98(2) states that customary law courts have no jurisdictions over criminal matters except those with customary interface, and have been referred to them by statutory courts. This Act, on the other hand, does not clearly define the criminal cases that have a customary interface. As a result, the courts hear any kinds of cases including homicide that do not fall in their jurisdictions. The Chief's Courts Ordinance of 1931 vested the customary courts

⁶ Kolok, Jame David, and Allan Ngari. "Citizens' perceptions on transitional justice processes in South Sudan." *ISS East Africa Report* 2019, no. 29 (2019)

⁷ Idris, Amir, ed. *South Sudan: Post-independence Dilemmas*. Routledge, 2018.

⁸ Deng, Justice Benjamin Baak. "Traditional Justice Methods and Their Possible Impact on Transitional Justice Models in South Sudan." *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law Online* 21

⁹ Bedigen, Winnifred. "Significance of Societal Customs in the South Sudan Civil War Resolution." *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development* 15, no. 1

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with full jurisdictions over all kind of criminal matters as opposed to the Local Government Act of 2009.

Customary courts play an imperative role in South Sudan's legal system. Customary law was the primary source of social order and stability in the southern region during the North-South civil war¹⁰. South Sudan struggled for many years to secure the customary laws which are based on traditions and customs¹¹. The and procedures and decisions of customary law courts are, in most cases, inconsistent with basic human right principles despite their increasing importance in the South Sudanese legal system. Such practices as compensation of murder with exchanger of a girl child and holding clan members or relatives collectively responsible for an individual clan member or relative's crime violates international human rights law¹². The basis of customary law is to achieve reconciliation and harmony within a community. However, the customary laws are largely seen to be achieving this at the expense of women and girls. It is still hard to come across a female chief in the customary law court benches despite the Local Government Act of 2009 providing for their inclusion and representation in the courts. In the face of these, it is hard for women to get justice when their individual rights are violated.

¹⁰ Babiker, Mohamed. "South Sudan's hybrid court: The challenge of redressing victims of international crimes." In *The Challenge of Governance in South Sudan*

¹¹ Olaf, Zenker, and Virgil Hoehne Markus. "Processing the paradox: when the state has to deal with customary law." In *The state and the paradox of customary law in Africa*

¹² Howell, Roy Carleton. "The Otieno Case: African Customary Law Versus Western Jurisprudence." In *Folk Law*

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The Local Government Act of 2009 provides for four levels of customary law courts. The level C courts are at the county levels and are the highest courts and receive and determine appeals from the level B courts. The level B courts are at Payams level with only jurisdictions up to maximum penalty. These courts are preceded by Town Bench Courts which are at town levels and have the competence of the Level B courts. The decision of these courts are appealed against before County Judge of the First Grade. The level A courts are the last and are at Boma levels, mainly dealing with family and marital issues.

Domestic customary law is the primary source of social order and stability within Southern Sudan, and acts as the basis of adjudication in the vast majority of civil and criminal cases¹³. The customary law was part and parcel of conflicting identities coexisting within the borders of the country during the North-South civil war, where the Northern Islamic Arabs wanted to project these elements and features of national identity determining the distribution of power, wealth and development opportunities. Each tribal group has its own discrete customary law body, resulting in over fifty separate customary law bodies. However, most tribal groups tend to have commonalities. As a result, customary law bodies collaborate to resolve inter-tribal disputes.

3.4 Independence of the judiciary

Customary law courts form part of the Judiciary of the nation of South Sudan. Independence of the judiciary remains one of the fundamental elements of modern democracy¹⁴.

¹³ Ibreck, Rachel, Hannah Logan, and Naomi Pendle. "Negotiating Justice: Courts as local civil authority during the conflict in South Sudan."

¹⁴ Collier, Paul. *The struggle for South Sudan: challenges of security and state formation*.

International human rights law provides for the independence of all levels of judiciary of the influence of the executive and legislative branches of the government as a threshold for fair trial, individual rights protection and obtaining effective remedy for any violation thereof from the other authorities of the state. Judiciary independence is in respect to the separation of powers principle which forms the cornerstone of the rule of law as reaffirmed in a number of international instruments regarding the judiciary.

The constitution of South Sudan provides of the independence of the judiciary of the influence of the executive and the legislative braches of the Government. The constitution states that judicial power is derived from the people and exercised by the courts in accordance with the customs, values, norms and aspiration of the people and in conformity with the law and the constitution¹⁵. The constitution of South Sudan also stipulates the upholding, promotion and respect of the independence of the judiciary and all its organs. The constitution also mandates all state institutions to execute judicial decisions¹⁶. The constitution also states that all members of the judiciary are subject to the constitution and the law, which shall be impartially applied by all judges at all judicial levels without political interference, fear or favor. In so doing, all judges, including customary law judges, are to be protected from reprisals as a consequent of their decisions.

Bloomsbury Publishing

¹⁵ Abotsi, E. Kofi. "Customary Law and the Rule of Law: Evolving Tensions and Re-Engineering." *Ariz. J. Int'l & Comp. L.* 37 (2020)

¹⁶ Kriesel, Julia. "Protecting groups in Africa: Between international law, national law, and local customary law." In *Normative Spaces and Legal Dynamics in Africa*

The people of South Sudan fought for decades for upholding of inter alia, human rights and fundamental freedoms. The country is, thus, founded on justice, equality, respect for traditions, respect of human dignity and fundamental freedoms. The customary law courts thus play a crucial role to the fulfilment of the struggles of the world's youngest nation.

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CHAPTER FOUR: HUMAN RIGHTS IN THE CUSTOMARY LAW COURTS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter expounds on how customary law courts in South Sudan have protected human rights and the consequent outcomes in the dispensation for parallelism between the customary and the statutory laws. The human rights are inherent to all individuals, irrespective of their nationality, gender, ethnicity, religion, color and place of residence. The chapter provides basic introduction to areas touching on human rights as provided by the customary law courts in South Sudan, and an in-depth analysis of how the statutory laws provide basis for enabling enjoyment of human rights. The section borrows from other jurisdiction on how human rights have been provided or barred as well as any discrepancies that might have arose from statutory and customary laws. Further the section addresses presence or absence of human rights as administered by the customary laws and the consequent effects they have on access to justice in the country. A closer look at the Transitional Constitution of South Sudan of 2011 is taken to inform possible discrepancies in protecting human rights.

Bill of Rights in the Transitional Constitution of South Sudan, 2011

Human right standards offer a fairness possibility in the three justice dimensions of structural, procedural and normative dimensions. Structural justice consists of participation and accountability with regards to groups rights including women, minorities and children¹⁷. Procedural justice encompasses adjudication process guidelines ensuring disputing parties are equally treated and their cases are decided by an impartial person with no interest in the case. Normative justice refers to the substantive rules protecting the vulnerable groups rights including children and women. The interim constitution of South Sudan has these concepts paid attention to in the bill of rights in terms of principles, procedures, and punishments/remedies available in the constitution, laws of the land and customary laws to ascertain the presence or absence of human rights and its effects on the process of justice in both the statute and customary law courts.

¹⁷ Roach, Steven C., and Derrick K. Hudson. "Introduction: The challenges of governance and peacebuilding in South Sudan." In *The Challenge of Governance in South Sudan*

The Interim Constitution of South Sudan contains the Bill of Rights in pages 9 to 20. The rights include right to life and human dignity, right to personal liberty, freedom from slavery, servitude and forced labor, equality before the law, right to found a family. The citizens of South Sudan also have the freedom from torture and the right to fair trial¹⁸. The right to litigation, protection from death penalty except in the cases of serious offences as stated by the law, freedom of assembly and association, freedom of expression and media, the right to participation and voting, freedom of movement and residence, the right to own property, the right to education, the right to access information, and the right to housing.

The rights are enshrined in the document include the right to life and human dignity as in Article 30, the right to liberty and security of persons in article 31, equality before the courts of law as in article 33, equal rights for men and women in article 34 and equal access to public health care in article 48 and the rights of women as stipulated in article 55.

Article 45 bases on Citizenship and Nationality as every person born to South Sudanese mother or father is awarded an inalienable right to citizenship and nationality. According to the ICSS, citizenship remains the basis of equal rights and duties for all South Sudanese, as every citizen enjoys all rights guaranteed by the Constitution. The legislature is mandated to develop laws regulating citizenship and naturalization. The National Government has exclusive legislative and executive powers over nationality and naturalization.

Article 29 of the ICSS awards every citizen the right to education and mandates all levels of Government to provide access to education without any form of discrimination along religious, race, ethnicity, gender and health status including HIV/AIDS or disability. All levels of Government are required to provide and ensure free and compulsory primary level education and provide free illiteracy eradication programmes.

Gender Mainstreaming, Women and Children Rights

The section also expounds on the aspects of gender mainstreaming, children and women rights as

¹⁸ Hoehne, Markus Virgil, and Olaf Zenker. "The State and the Paradox of Customary Law in Africa."

advanced by the customary justice system.

Article 16 stipulates affirmative action as women rights to participate equally with men in public life as all government levels are mandated to promote this. Women also have the right to own property and share in the estates of deceased husbands together with other legal heirs. The article also awards women the right to equal pay for work and other related benefits with men. Article 21 protects pregnant and lactating women from death penalty. Article 35 bases on employment rights and protection as it states that the constitution be interpreted and applied to advance individual dignity and address the needs of the people. Article 122 of the ICSS also enshrines a substantial representation of women in the judiciary with regard to competence, integrity, credibility and impartiality. Article 139 states that the Civil service be governed by inter alia representing the diverse population of South Sudan based on ability, fair competition for jobs, the need to redress imbalances of the past to achieve a diverse representation. Article 142 mandates the National Government to ensure at least 25% of institution and commission membership be women. Article 166 mandates local governments to ensure gender mainstreaming in local government¹⁹. Article 202 stipulates establishment of the President of the Republic Commission, the National Constitution Review Commission with due regard to gender, political, social and regional diversity of South Sudan recognizing inclusiveness, transparency and equitable participation²⁰. The filling of the commission membership pays attention to competence and technical expertise and experience. The constitution also mandates both National and State Governments to legislatively and executively promote women empowerment and Gender policy.

Children rights include the right to life, survival and development, right to religion, worship, and assemble, the right to a name and nationality, the right to know and be cared for by parents or legal guardians, the right from exploitative practices and abuse, the right not to service in the army nor

¹⁹ Seidel, Katrin. "Local law and dispute resolution mechanisms under negotiation in emerging South Sudan." In *Comparative Dispute Resolution*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020.

²⁰ Katrin, Seidel. "When the state is forced to deal with local law: approaches of and challenges for state actors in emerging South Sudan." In *The state and the paradox of customary law in Africa*

performing hazardous work harmful to their education, health or well-being²¹. They also have a right to be free from corporal punishment and cruel and inhuman treatment, the right from being subjected to negative and harmful cultural practices that affect their wealth, education, welfare or dignity and the right to be protected from abduction and trafficking. Children are also protected from death penalties.

Discrepancies between Statutory and customary laws and linkages to human rights

The case of Namibia presents a comparison to South Sudan law, where some statutory laws contravene the constitutional principles of human rights. For instance, in Namibia, women are denied rights to land ownership through the Administration of Estates Act (1965), Administration of Estates Proclamation of 1941, the Intestate Succession Ordinance of 1946 and the Native Administration Proclamation of 1928. While the Article 66 of the Namibian constitution granted that both common law and customary law at independence were legitimate and did not contradict/conflict the law, they were to coexist. Despite the law covering both customary and the common laws, women still face discrimination based on their sex.

The customary law courts make their rulings according to the customary laws of the respective ethnic groups while the formal courts are guided by the principles laid down by the constitution and laws in their dispute resolution roles²². There is no clear relationship between the working of the two court systems in South Sudan.

Customary courts still play major roles in South Sudan's legal system. Customary law are still the primary source of social order and stability in the southern even in the present

²¹ BARCIK, Jacek. "STATE BUILDING ON THE EXEMPLE OF SOUTH SUDAN. LEGAL AND HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE." *ROK XI NUMER 3/2018 (40)* (2018): 43.

²² Zenker, Olaf, and Markus Virgil Höhne, eds. *The state and the paradox of customary law in Africa*. Routledge

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day as over 60% of cases are resolved by them²³. The customary laws are based on traditions and customs. The procedures and decisions made by these traditional courts are, in most cases, inconsistent with basic human right principles and the constitutional bill of rights despite their increasing importance in the South Sudanese legal system²⁴. The courts practice of restoration and compensation such as the compensation of murder with exchanger of a girl child and holding clan members or relatives collectively responsible for an individual clan member or relative's crime violates international human rights law. Customary law tries to achieve reconciliation and harmony within a community. However, the customary laws are largely seen to be achieving this at the expense of women and girls²⁵.

Each tribal group has its own discrete customary law body, resulting in over fifty separate customary law bodies. However, most tribal groups have similar customs. Most of these practices and traditions, whose dispute resolution is based on mediation, restoration and compensation principles, are in most cases in conflict with the bill of rights and statutory laws²⁶. The most affected right or freedom in the constitution pertains to equality before the law in relation to discrimination based on gender, sex, right to fair trial, protection against inhuman and

²³ Seidel, Katrin. "Local law and dispute resolution mechanisms under negotiation in emerging South Sudan." In *Comparative Dispute Resolution*.

²⁴ Hinz, Manfred O. "The ascertainment of Namibian customary law completed: What has been done and what lies ahead." *Beyond a Quarter Century of Constitutional Democracy* (2017): 1.

²⁵ Hove, Mediel, and Enock Ndawana. "Women's Rights in Jeopardy: The Case of War-Torn South Sudan." *Sage open* 7, no. 4

²⁶ Musila, Godfrey. "The Rule of Law and the Role of Customary Courts in Stabilizing South Sudan." *Special Report No. 4*

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degrading treatment and harmful practices against women such as using girls in compensation in blood disputes or settling murder cases and sentencing people to non-judicial corporal punishment.

The customary laws, and hence customary law court verdicts, are in constant contradiction with modern constitutional democracy and modern human rights values and the moral and ethics set by the constitution as the supreme law of the land. This is due to the reason that customary laws have no legal provision in statute laws that prescribes procedures, punishments and sentences that can be imposed by these traditional courts.

The Bill of Rights as in the TCSS were formed in line with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The principles of equality and non-discrimination are among the constitutional guides to equal protection of all citizens by the law as they are all entitled to equal protection regardless of race, ethnicity, color, sex, language, creed, political opinion, birth, locality and social status²⁷. These provisions are not, in most cases, followed by customary law especially in matters pertaining to domestic violence. Women reporting such cases against their husbands fail to get justice as the customary laws allow a certain level of violence in homes and permit disciplining of wives²⁸. Women are also sentenced by these courts for failing in their traditional duties such as failing to cook for their husbands, insulting them, and drinking which are contrary to customary laws but within statute laws. With regards to the spirit of the constitution of South Sudan, this is discriminatory as women are not accorded same opportunities and promote cultural

²⁷ Turuk, Mut. "Applicability of Customary and Statutory Law in South Sudan: A Jurisprudential Perspective."

²⁸ Adong, Nyinypiu. "INTIMATE PARTNER VIOLENCE IN SOUTH SUDAN." *Development* 6

prejudices that result in widespread women discrimination. This offends the constitutional concept of equality²⁹. This practices also contravene the concept of right to litigation guaranteed to all persons under the Transitional constitution. Women can also be punished under customary laws for reporting an abusive husband and are morally discouraged from reporting another case. Ignorance and lack of legal aid awareness, creation of access to justice support for women also complicate matters as there is general support for the customary practices. These conflict Article 20 of the transitional constitution stating that no person shall be denied the right to resort to courts of law to redress grievances against individuals, organizations or the Government.

Article 19 of the transitional constitution talks on the provisions on the right to fair trial and courts, including customary courts, are required accord all parties a fair trial as key to the integrity of legal proceedings³⁰. Customary laws come short in the achievement of this constitutional principle especial in cases between men and women, highly respected members of the society and disadvantaged groups like the poor and cases with local governments and local judicial leaders³¹. The composition of the court itself denies women a chance to fair trial as the chief presiding over the customary courts are generally older men deeply ingrained in patriarch views influencing their decisions, viewpoints and judgments. The chiefs are lenient to men

²⁹ Edward, Jane Kani. "Conflict, customary law, gender, and women's rights in South Sudan." In *South Sudan*

³⁰ Kuer, Tong K. "An Analysis Of The Right Against Torture In South Sudan." PhD diss., University of Nairobi, 2017.

³¹ Edward, Jane Kani. "Conflict, customary law, gender, and women's rights in South Sudan." In *South Sudan*, pp. 57-73. Routledge, 2018.

interest. Article 19 (3) of the TCSS states that all litigants in criminal and civil proceedings are entitled to fair trial and public hearing. Customary law courts are held out in the open, usually under large trees with more men than women attending making them more intimidating for a woman under trial or forwarding case³². This is worse in rape cases where women are made to make full accounts even if they are embarrassing, which demoralizes them from testifying³³. The use of uncontested evidence also further denies litigants the right to fair trial as unverifiable evidence such as witch craft are used to deliver judgements. Furthermore, customary law courts also employ practices that discriminate against female rape victims and may affect their ability to marry and the amount of bride wealth she can generate for her family. This contravenes Article 15 of the TCSS, 2011 which states gives every marriageable aged person the right to marry opposite sex and found a family. Family laws restrict marriage without their free and full consent.

With regards to gender equality as reinforced by the constitution, it is still hard for women to hold positions in the customary law courts such female chiefs in the customary law court benches despite the Local Government Act of 2009 providing for their inclusion and

³² Edwards, Sarah. "Making it stick: navigating the paradox of gender mainstreaming through frictional encounters in South Sudan."

³³ Kolok, Jame David, Maram Mahdi, and Allan Ngari. "Land and reparative justice in South Sudan."

representation in the courts³⁴. In the face of these, it is hard for women to get justice when their individual rights are violated³⁵.

Customary law courts in the country also prevalently apply corporal punishment upon conviction. These are applied in cases of adultery, domestic violence, theft, disturbing public order and dishonesty. South Sudan lacks written laws prescribing corporal punishments. Article 18 of the constitution protects all citizens against torture, inhumane and degrading treatment. Customary courts contravene this by applying such punishments as flogging, caning and whipping as a form of punishment.

The use of girls for compensation is a common remedy for murder under customary law for the perpetrator and their family to compensate the victim's family for the loss. The compensation can take different forms depending on the resources available to that community. Section 98 (3) of the Local Government Act, 2009 provides for adequate compensation to victims and voluntary mediation and reconciliation agreements between parties be recognized and forced. This is in line with customary law principle of restorative justice and lack of police and prison services. Every child has the right to be protected from early marriage, forced circumcision, tattooing, scarification, piercing, tooth removal and any other cultural right likely to affect their health, welfare, dignity, physical, emotional, psychological, mental and intellectual developments. Removing a girl from her home exposes the child to the violation of the above stated rights.

³⁴ Hove, Mediel, and Enock Ndawana. "Women's Rights in Jeopardy: The Case of War-Torn South Sudan." *Sage open* 7, no. 4

³⁵ Zenker, Olaf, and Markus Virgil Höhne, eds. *The state and the paradox of customary law in Africa*.

Conclusion of the chapter

The ongoing acceptance of customary practices violate human rights in the customary law courts as a result of weak justice system and cultural conservatism. To mitigate this, security should be provided to the chiefs involved in these decision making, supported by robust civic education as legislation alone without legal awareness for both justice systems cannot stop human rights abuse/violation. The Government of South Sudan should work to strengthen the justice systems and ensure the spirit of the constitution is reflected in all judicial rulings to protect human rights.

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